

Soil Sampling results at Vallon de Nant

Soil moisture measurements, granulometry and infiltrometry

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Table des matières

1	Methods	2
1.1	Soil Sampling and granulometry	2
1.1.1	Physical description of the sampling sites	2
1.1.2	Sampling method and laser granulometry	2
1.1.3	Soil parameters (pedotransfer functions)	3
1.2	Infiltrometry test	3
1.2.1	The Beerkan infiltration method	3
1.2.2	BEST analysis method	3
1.3	Soil moisture measurements	4
2	Results	5
2.1	Granulometry and soil parameters results	5
2.2	Infiltrometry results	5
2.3	Soil moisture results	6

This technical report presents the methods applied for soil sampling, granulometry analysis and infiltrometry test for soil study in Vallon de Nant. Continuous soil moisture measurements are also presented. This report is a notice related to soil data (particule size distribution and soil moisture time series) uploaded on Zenodo.

1 Methods

1.1 Soil Sampling and granulometry

1.1.1 Physical description of the sampling sites

See map figure 1 for location of the 9 sampling points.

- **Auberge** : (1257 m a.s.l.) The sampling point is located near the weather station but outside of the station fence. The vegetation at the sampling point is cut grass, without grazing (the point is located before the cow's fence in spring). The soil on this point is globally not walked nor trampled.
- **Pissenlit** : (1281 m a.s.l.) The sampling point is located approximately 500 m upstream from the *Auberge* point, in the grazed meadow with sparse conifers along the Nant river. The vegetation at the point is grazed grass and the soil is walked. Surface runoff is observed in the vicinity of the point.
- **Chalet** : (1491 m a.s.l.) The sampling point is located around 100 m from the alpine chalet building. The vegetation is short grass, grazed and poorly developed. The soil at this point is very thin and rocky, above the ancien morain deposit.
- **Petit Pont** : (1473 m a.s.l.) The sampling point is located on the left river bank, near the wooden bridge on the Nant river. Vegetation is relatively short, grazed grass. Soil is deep and developed at this point. This point is located in accumulation area of the dropping cone from the shisty LaChaux cliff.
- **Argile** : (1473 m a.s.l.) This point is very similar to the *Petit Pont* point, but located at the exact point of the soil moisture sensor, about 50 m from the bridge. The soil is deep and walked by the cows and the vegetation is not-so-short, grazed grass.
- **Protegee** : (1479 m a.s.l.) This point is located within the protected area on the left river bank, delimited by a fence, in the major bed of the river. The vegetation is dense and developed, with a lot of diversity. The soil is very thin : about 5 cm of black, organic loam followed by ~ 10cm of coarser soil. The root density is the loamy horizon is high. This point is not grazed.
- **LaChaux** : (1777 m a.s.l.) The sampling point is located at the LaChaux weather station and soil moisture measurement point. Vegetation is dense and high Rumex plant, usually present on densely pastured area (this area is a resting point of the cows). Vegetation diversity on this point is low. Soil is deep and developed. The area is an accumulation zone for the erosion from the surrounding cliffs.
- **Combe** : (1853 m a.s.l.) This sampling point is location at about 400 m up hill from the LaChaux point, in a small thalweg (combe). The vegetation is dense and diverse at the point. The root zone at the sampling point is dense. The soil is relatively developed, on top of an accumulation of large moraine rocks. The area is mainly not grazed. Several springs are located down stream (about 50 m) of the sampling point.
- **Bastion** : (2497 m a.s.l.) This point is located right below the Perris Blanc cliffs, in the accumulation zone of the rock fall. The area is mainly mineral, vegetation is sparse and low. Soil is thin and poorly developed. The infiltrometry test is not performed at this point because there was no water available.

1.1.2 Sampling method and laser granulometry

For each of these 9 points, an auger hole is dug (length of the auger = 1.30m). Since digging a larger pit is not permitted in the reserve, what is taken out from the auger hole is used to describe the soil vertical at the sampling point. Main horizons are described (color, root and rock density, general density). Samples are taken from the auger sampling at different depths. For the deep soils, main types of soil are selected (not every horizon are sampled). 2 to 6 samples are taken for each point. Soils below 1.30m are not described.

Granulometry analysis is then performed for each of the 37 resulting samples. The laser granulometry method, available at Unil is used. The protocol applied is as follows :

- The samples are sieved at 2 mm to extract the coarse fraction
- 1 to 2 g of material are taken, homogeneously grabbed from each sample
- Organic matter is destroyed by adding H₂O₂ for 10 days, with pH correction

- A deflocculant is added the night before the analysis
- Laser analysis is performed for each sample. A particule size distribution is obtained, for grain sizes from 0.003 μm to 2 mm.

1.1.3 Soil parameters (pedotransfer functions)

The hydraulic properties of the soils at the sampling points are computed from the results of the granulometry analysis. The empirical pedotransfer functions proposed by Clapp and Hornberger (1978) are used to compute values of soil water content at saturation (w_{sat}), wilting point (w_{wilt}) and field capacity (w_{fc}) from the CLAY and SAND fraction for each sample. The applied formula are given Table 1. The soil parameters are computed for each depths and then averaged on the soil vertical to get one value for each of the 8 sampling point.

Name		Units	Formula
Soil water content at saturation	w_{sat}	m^3/m^3	$(-1.08.SAND + 494.305) * 10^{-3}$
Wilting point	w_{wilt}	m^3/m^3	$37.1342 * 10^{-3} * CLAY^{0.5}$
Field capacity	w_{fc}	m^3/m^3	$89.0497 * 10^{-3} * CLAY^{0.3495}$

TABLE 1 – Empirical pedotransfer functions proposed by Clapp and Hornberger (1978) applied to compute values of soil water content at saturation (w_{sat}), wilting point (w_{wilt}) and field capacity (w_{fc}) from the CLAY and SAND fraction for each sample.

1.2 Infiltrometry test

See map figure 1 for location of the 8 infiltration points.

1.2.1 The Beerkan infiltration method

The simple Beerkan infiltration method is used to determine the infiltration rates at saturation at the sampling points. This method is detailed by (Haverkamp et al., 1994) and (Braud et al., 2005). A document published as part of the SoLAB project (www.itab.asso.fr/programmes/solab.php) offer 'best practices' for setting up a BeerKan test. A PVC cylinder of diameter **25 cm** is used, and **1 L** of water is used at poured at each iteration. The resulting water load is **20.37 mm** at each iteration.

The following protocol is applied :

- The vegetation at the tested point is cut but the soil is not disturbed, including root zone.
- The PVC cylinder of (diameter 25 cm) is used. It is slightly pressed in the soil to avoid lateral flows. The outer edges can be sealed with moistened earth.
- An *anti-splash* plastic is used to avoid alteration of the surface when pouring water.
- Start of the experiment : place the 'anti-splash' plastic and pour the contents of a bottle (1L).
- Iteration : we stop the stopwatch at each iteration when 1) a large part of the surface is no longer shiny (the layer of water has disappeared) and 2) the last 'little puddle' has dried up.
- End of the experiment : we repeat until we have close infiltration times at least twice.

1.2.2 BEST analysis method

The method for estimating retention curves and hydraulic conductivities BEST (Beerkan estimation of soil transfer parameters) is described in detail by (Lassabatère et al., 2006). BEST is approaching the series of cumulative infiltration rates $I(t)$ and instantaneous infiltration rates $q(t)$ by the expressions provided by (Haverkamp et al., 1994), which involves the sorptivity S and the hydraulic conductivity at K_{sat} saturation of the soil. $K(\theta)$ and $h(\theta)$ are established according to (Van Genuchten, 1980; Burdine, 1953; Brooks and Corey, 1966). These expressions involve three parameters of form which are determined from grain size distributions (i.e. particle size) (Fuentes et al., 2017) and based on capillarity models (Haverkamp et al., 1994).

1.3 Soil moisture measurements

See map figure 1 for location of the 3 soil moisture measurement points.

The 5TM/DECAGON capacitive instrument is used to record soil moisture and soil temperature at the hourly time step at different depth at 3 points in the catchment. The location of the 3 5TM/DECAGON soil moisture and soil temperature sensors, and depth of the sensors are presented on Table 2. 4 depths (on 4 slots) are instrumented at the Auberge point and 2 at the PetitPont (also called Chalet) and LaChaux points. But for PetitPont and LaChaux, only the sensor at 25 cm depth did actually work. The sensors were installed in August 2021 and are still on site. At the Auberge point, the 5 cm sensor is actually the sensor initially installed for the SensorScope weather station, but since this station was not functioning anymore, the sensor was keep in soil and plugged into the DECAGON logger on November, 07 2022.

Point	LAT	LON	ALT m.a.s.l.	Sensor Depth			
				Slot 1	Slot 2	Slot 3	Slot 4
Auberge	46.251	7.110	1257	10 cm	20 cm	30 cm	5 cm
PetitPont	46.231	7.102	1473	25 cm	<i>40 cm</i>	-	-
LaChaux	46.229	7.092	1777	25 cm	<i>40 cm</i>	-	-

TABLE 2 – Location of the 3 5TM/DECAGON soil moisture and soil temperature sensors, and depth of the sensors for each point. The depths in italic did not work correctly for the recording period.

FIGURE 1 – Location of the soil sampling and infiltrometry points.

2 Results

2.1 Granulometry and soil parameters results

Table 3 present the CLAY, SAND and SILT fraction resulting from the laser granulometry analysis for the 36 samples, together with the w_{sat} , w_{wilt} and field capacity w_{fc} computed through the (Clapp and Hornberger, 1978) equation for each sample. Figure 2 present the texture triangle for the 36 samples using the USDA soil texture classification with the results of the laser granulometry analysis. All the samples are in the SiltyLoam category, what is consistent with morain silty deposits. In addition, this result is consistent with previous works in Vallon de Nant.

FIGURE 2 – Triangle of texture for the 36 samples using the USDA soil texture classification. All the samples are in the SiltyLoam category.

Available data on Zenedo :

- Particule size distributions for the 36 samples

2.2 Infiltrometry results

Figure 3 shows the infiltration time (in minutes) versus iteration number for each of the 8 infiltration tests performed. These values are analysed through the BEST method to get the hydraulic conductivity at saturation rates (K_{sat}). Table 4 gives the resulting values of K_{sat} , together with the values of $\%clay$, $\%silt$, $\%sand$, w_{sat} , w_{wilt} and w_{fc} averaged on the soil vertical for each measurement points. The values of K_{sat} obtained are consistent with general values considered by Cosby et al. (1984) for soil classes.

The value of K_{sat} for the *Auberge* point is significantly higher than for the other points. This can be explained by 1) the relatively important fraction of sand at this point and 2) the impact of soil trampling and grazing. Indeed, the second higher K_{sat} value is the *Combe* point and these two points have the particularity of being non grazed. Figure 4 present the infiltrometry results for 2 pairs of points : *Auberge-Pissenlit* and *LaChaux-Combe*. *Auberge* and *Combe* are not grazed and *Pissenlit* and *LaChaux* are grazed. This graph shows that the infiltration times are significantly longer on grazed points than on non grazed points.

	Point	id	depth (cm)	%clay	%silt	%sand	w_{sat} (m^3/m^3)	w_{wilt} (m^3/m^3)	w_{fc} (m^3/m^3)
1	Auberge	1	0-14	15.168	60.866	23.966	0.468	0.145	0.23
2	Auberge	2	14-20	15.8	61.609	22.591	0.47	0.148	0.234
3	Auberge	2Bis	14-10	15.745	61.898	22.357	0.47	0.147	0.233
4	Auberge	3	20-25	14.929	61.302	23.769	0.469	0.143	0.229
5	Auberge	4	25-32	15.176	61.653	23.171	0.469	0.145	0.23
6	Auberge	5	34-42	14.086	59.771	26.143	0.466	0.139	0.224
7	Auberge	6	42-49	13.455	56.217	30.328	0.462	0.136	0.221
8	Bastion	1	23-33	18.08	65.289	16.632	0.476	0.158	0.245
9	Bastion	2	45-55	15.524	61.466	23.01	0.469	0.146	0.232
10	Bastion	3	55-65	15.021	63.025	21.953	0.471	0.144	0.23
11	Chalet	1	0-10	15.216	72.758	12.026	0.481	0.145	0.231
12	Chalet	2	10-20	13.092	66.758	20.15	0.473	0.134	0.219
13	Chalet	3	20-30	14.092	71.056	14.852	0.478	0.139	0.224
14	Combe	1	0-15	17.356	63.547	19.097	0.474	0.155	0.241
15	Combe	2	15-20	16.543	64.369	19.089	0.474	0.151	0.237
16	Combe	3	44-54	13.662	61.83	24.508	0.468	0.137	0.222
17	Combe	4	75-82	14.984	62.861	22.155	0.47	0.144	0.229
18	Combe	5	115-124	12.9	57.613	29.487	0.462	0.133	0.218
19	LaChaux	1	0-10	15.517	63.393	21.09	0.472	0.146	0.232
20	LaChaux	2	10-20	16.1	63.968	19.932	0.473	0.149	0.235
21	LaChaux	3	32-40	12.036	63.538	24.426	0.468	0.129	0.212
22	LaChaux	3Bis	32-40	11.911	62.352	25.737	0.467	0.128	0.212
23	LaChaux	4	40-60	12.704	65.8	21.496	0.471	0.132	0.217
24	LaChaux	5	60-70	12.755	61.343	25.902	0.466	0.133	0.217
25	LaChaux	6	70-80	13.125	63.713	23.161	0.469	0.135	0.219
26	LaChaux	7	80-100	10.517	58.004	31.479	0.46	0.12	0.203
27	PetitPont	1	0-13	15.378	67.783	16.839	0.476	0.146	0.231
30	PetitPont	4	35-44	16.789	72.831	10.38	0.483	0.152	0.239
31	PetitPont	5	80-90	14.137	71.574	14.289	0.479	0.14	0.225
28	PetitPont-Argile	2	0-15	19.117	69.899	10.984	0.482	0.162	0.25
29	PetitPont-Argile	3	15-45	17.357	71.091	11.551	0.482	0.155	0.241
32	PetitPont-Argile	6	115-130	10.407	50.606	38.987	0.452	0.12	0.202
33	Pissenlit	1	0-10	14.741	72.686	12.573	0.481	0.143	0.228
34	Pissenlit	2	15-25	19.794	69.268	10.938	0.482	0.165	0.253
35	Protegee	1	0-5	11.862	61.616	26.522	0.466	0.128	0.211
36	Protegee	2	5-7	6.334	42.235	51.431	0.439	0.093	0.17

TABLE 3 – Granulometry results for the 36 samples and estimation of w_{sat} , w_{wilt} and field capacity w_{fc} , through the (Clapp and Hornberger, 1978) equation. The indicated depth is the depth of the material sampling.

2.3 Soil moisture results

Figure 5 shows the hourly time series of soil moisture measurements divided by the content at saturation (WC/W_{sat}) at the 3 points measurements for the different depths. This data can be used for further analysis for soil water resposn, in particular with regards to snow melt.

Available data on Zenedo :

- Time series of soil moisture at each depth for the 3 measurements points

FIGURE 3 – Infiltration time (in minutes) versus iteration number for each of the 8 infiltration points.

	Point	depth (cm)	%clay	%silt	%sand	w_{sat}	w_{wilt} (m^3/m^3)	w_{fc} (m^3/m^3)	K_{sat} ($mm.h^{-1}$)
1	Auberge	69	14.908	60.474	24.618	0.468	0.143	0.229	860.378
2	Bastion	65	16.208	63.26	20.532	0.472	0.149	0.236	NA
3	Chalet	32	14.133	70.191	15.676	0.477	0.139	0.225	59.049
4	Combe	90	15.089	62.044	22.867	0.47	0.144	0.229	185.429
5	LaChaux	>130	13.083	62.764	24.153	0.468	0.134	0.218	20.212
6	PetitPont	>130	15.531	67.297	17.172	0.476	0.146	0.231	97.682
7	Pissenlit	40	17.267	70.977	11.756	0.482	0.154	0.24	79.197
8	Protegee	10	9.098	51.926	38.977	0.452	0.11	0.19	127.681

TABLE 4 – Granulometry results for the 8 sampling points and vertical average value of w_{sat} , w_{wilt} , w_{fc} through the (Clapp and Hornberger, 1978) equation, and conductivity at saturation through the *BEST* method. The indicated depth is the total depth of the soil column.

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FIGURE 4 – Infiltration time (in minutes) versus iteration number for 4 infiltration points : 2 are grazed points (LaChaux, Pissenlit) and 2 are non-grazed points (Auberge, Combe).

FIGURE 5 – Soil moisture measurements divided by the content at saturation (WC/W_{sat}) at the 3 points measurements for the different depths.

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